

IMI2 821520 - ConcePTION

ConcePTION

WP6 – Cross-stakeholder engagement, endorsement and adoption

D6.2 Report explaining the regulatory procedures, their scientific requirements, priorities and decision-making pathways regarding the use of medicines in pregnancy and lactation

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Abstract

IMI ConcePTION is developing new methods and establishing new pipelines for the generation of evidence on the appropriate (safe and effective) use of medicines in pregnancy and during breast feeding. It is doing this because there are ethical difficulties with generating evidence in the classical and well accepted method: through randomised controlled trials (RCTs). This new evidence is largely being derived from real-world data (e.g. longitudinal observational studies, registries, electronic health records, pharmacovigilance), from animal models and simulations, *in vitro* human and animal cell-based models and by scaling up the availability of breast milk samples through a network of milk bio-banks.

ConcePTION aims to bridge major gaps in the field of pregnancy and breastfeeding pharmacovigilance with the ultimate outcome being the formation of an ecosystem that provides a regulatory endorsed framework and approach for the collation, analysis, interpretation and communication of data collected in Work Package (WP)1 (routine health care and surveillance data), WP2 (exposed pregnancy reports) WP 3 & 4 (animal models and lactation exposures) according to a structured and co-ordinated approach.

This task will help all consortium partners and external stakeholders to share a common understanding of the scope, roles and responsibilities of regulatory agencies and their decision-making pathways when assessing new evidence on the use of medicines in pregnancy and lactation.

This deliverable builds on information gathered in Deliverable 6.1 in the space of engaging with Regulators and outlines the steps being proposed within ConcePTION as we look to engage with the regulatory authorities.

One of the highest impact outcomes of ConcePTION will be the formal endorsement of new methodologies to generate or validate evidence by regulators, in particular EMA. EMA has the mechanism of Qualification Advice (QA), as one pathway that could be utilised. WP6 has run webinars to help educate the consortium about these EMA channels (with input from our EMA partner), and identified future candidate topics that might be considered for one of these channels.

In the following years of the project WP6 anticipates putting the content of these chapters into action, in particular, through providing expert advice to other WPs on their regulatory engagements and partner with teams as they navigate through the different regulatory pathways

This deliverable also outlines the work that has been done in producing a project wide Glossary that has been developed for consortium wide use.

The ConcePTION project brings together many partners from different backgrounds including maternal health, medicines development, pharmacovigilance, clinical and life sciences research, mathematical modelling, health informatics, multiple stakeholder representatives and other disciplines. It aims to develop new forms of evidence that require very precisely formulated specification and documentation. For this reason, a project wide glossary was included in the description of action to be developed by WP6.

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1. Regulatory Engagement

Introduction

Currently during the development of new medicines there is limited to no information within the product labels on the safety of medications taken during pregnancy on the pregnancy outcomes at initial launch of a drug. Product labels almost always recommend against breastfeeding as the risks are poorly characterized and there are restrictions to clinical research in pregnant and lactating women. Animal models (mostly rat) are not predictive of humans & human lactation studies are time consuming and costly. Frequently health authorities (HA) request a pregnancy registry at the time of initial approval and data from spontaneous pregnancy reports through pharmacovigilance are not fully utilized, quality and consistency as well as analysis can be improved.

In order to see tangible benefits within the R&D sector ConcePTION aims to create a paradigm shift in how we generate and disseminate evidence on the effects of medication in pregnancy from existing health data and newly collected data.

Landscape Analysis Outcomes: supporting ConcePTION Strategy

A key focus for ConcePTION Project is to provide validated and regulatory endorsed workflows for fast, optimised evidence generation. By doing this, Regulatory bodies will be able to review data generated by individual sponsors that use the same broadly acceptable methodologies, hence making review of the individual product datasets easier.

- Animal and in-silico lactation models with higher predictability for humans & improved PKPD model: methodology(ies) presented to Regulatory Bodies for consideration, review and endorsement thus providing more reliable predictions for initial labelling
- Human milk biobank enabling faster and cost-effective analysis of the levels of active substances transferred in breastmilk, Better characterisation and prediction of the transfer of medicines in breast milk / transfer to the infant will deliver more reliable data to inform the initial label.
- Advancing clinical and healthcare practice: Scientifically sound and validated information via evidence generation for implementation into the regulatory guidelines, which will lead to better information for HCPs and patients, and generally improve the health of our next generation.
- The faster and more efficient way of producing data to assess medication-related adverse pregnancy outcomes will enable regulatory bodies to include enhanced information in the label, providing prescribers and patients with much needed information to guide treatment decisions for the benefit of women and children.
- Unified regulatory framework for collecting case reports of exposures to medicines during pregnancy to improve and quicken the generation and analysis of pregnancy outcomes, both positive and negative.
- HAs to consider alternative approaches to pregnancy registries based on real world evidence

Role of Regulators

Regulatory authority and organizations are responsible for effective drug regulation required to ensure the safety, efficacy and quality of drugs, as well as the accuracy and appropriateness of the drug information available to the public. Regulatory bodies provide strategic, tactical and operational direction and support for working within regulations to expedite the development and delivery of safe and effective healthcare products to individuals around the world. Every country has its own regulatory agencies which are responsible to enforce the rules and regulations and issue the guidelines to regulate drug development process, licensing, registration, manufacturing, marketing and labelling of pharmaceutical products. Click [here](#) for List of national competent authorities in the EEA

The European Medicines Agency (EMA) works closely with the national competent authorities of the Member States of the European Union (EU) and the European Economic Area (EEA) responsible for human medicines. The national competent authorities are primarily responsible for the authorization of medicines available in the EU that do not pass through the centralized procedure. They also supply thousands of [European experts](#) who serve as members of the EMA Agency's scientific committees, working parties or in assessment teams supporting their members.

Regulatory authorities act as a guardian that ensures the safety, efficacy and quality of medicines drugs available to the public, to identify the strengths and weaknesses of drug regulation and to propose strategies to improve drug regulation.

World Health Organization (WHO), Pan American Health Organization (PAHO), World Trade Organization (WTO), International Conference on Harmonization (ICH), World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) are some of the international regulatory agencies and organizations who are also involved in all aspects of pharmaceutical regulations related to drug product registration, manufacturing, distribution, price control, marketing, research and development, and intellectual property protection.

European Medicines Regulatory Network

The system for regulating medicines in Europe is unique in the world. It is based on a closely-coordinated regulatory network of national competent authorities in the Member States of the European Economic Area (EEA) working together with the European Medicines Agency (EMA) and the European Commission (EC).

The [European medicines regulatory network](#) is the cornerstone of EMA's work and success. The Agency operates at the heart of the network, coordinating and supporting interactions between over fifty national competent authorities for both human and veterinary medicines.

These national authorities supply thousands of European experts to take part in EMA's scientific committees, working parties and other groups.

The regulatory network also includes the [European Commission](#), whose principal role in the European system is to take binding decisions based on the scientific recommendations delivered by EMA.

By working closely together, this network ensures that safe, effective and high-quality medicines are authorized throughout the European Union (EU), and that patients, healthcare professionals and citizens are provided with adequate and consistent information about medicines.

The mission of the [European Medicines Agency](#) (EMA) is to foster scientific excellence in the evaluation and supervision of medicines, for the benefit of public and animal health in the European Union (EU). EMA is committed to enabling timely patient access to new medicines, and plays a vital role in supporting medicine development for the benefit of patients.

What we do

Protect human and animal health

- Facilitate development and access to medicines
- Evaluate applications for marketing authorisation
- Monitor the safety of medicines across their life cycle
- ABC** Provide reliable information on human and veterinary medicines in lay language
XΨΩ

EU Medicines Agencies Network Strategy to 2020

Focus on key public health priorities including availability and AMR	Ensure timely access to new beneficial and safe medicines for patients	Increase availability & promote development of innovative medicines	Promote 'better regulation'
Strengthen regulatory capability & transparency	Support for patient focused innovation & contribute to a vibrant life science sector	Focus on key public and animal health priorities including AMR	Improve the functioning of the internal market
Reinforce the scientific and regulatory capacity of the network	Strive for operational excellence	Assure product supply chain and data integrity	Convergence of global standards and contribution to international fora
Strengthen the links with other authorities and with stakeholders	Ensure effective communication of and within the network	Support training and capacity building and promote the EU regulatory model	Ensure best use of resources through promoting mutual reliance & work sharing

towards a system that

- is more agile
- more likely to deliver innovative medicine
- meets unmet medical needs
- fosters excellence, incl:
- effective use of resources available across the EU
- is patient focused
- promotes better regulation
- ensures effective communication

http://www.ema.europa.eu/ema/index.jsp?curl=pages/about_us/general/general_content_000292.jsp&mid=WC0b01ac05800293a4

Source: IMI Webinar How to engage with regulators EMA / FDA 6 Dec 2017

Options for Engagement

The Agency uses a wide range of regulatory mechanisms to achieve engagement, which are continuously reviewed and improved. These mechanisms include:

- [support for early access](#);
- [scientific advice and protocol assistance](#);
- [paediatric procedures](#);
- scientific support for [advanced-therapy medicines](#);
- [orphan designation](#) of medicines for rare diseases;
- [scientific guidelines](#) on requirements for the quality, safety and [efficacy](#) testing of medicines;
- the [Innovation Task Force](#), a forum for early dialogue with applicants.

EMA also plays a role in supporting research and innovation in the pharmaceutical sector, and promotes innovation and development of new medicines by European micro-, small- and medium-sized-enterprises.

A Webinar was held in Sep 2020 where the consortium members were provided information related to the Role of Regulators, what this means for ConcePTION and what avenues are appropriate for ConcePTION to explore. Please refer to Appendix 1 for content of presentation.

Qualification Advice European Medicines Agency (EMA)

The EMA qualification of novel methodologies is a voluntary scientific pathway to establish the regulatory acceptability of a specific use of a methodology for the development of medicinal products. Outcomes of this pathway are:

- Committee for Medicinal Products for Human Use (CHMP) adoption of qualification advice on future protocols and methods for further method development towards qualification, based on the evaluation of the scientific rationale and on preliminary data submitted.
 - Based on qualification advice, the Agency may propose a letter of support as an option, when the novel methodology under evaluation cannot yet be qualified but is shown to be promising based on preliminary data.

- Letters of support aim to encourage data-sharing and to facilitate studies aimed at eventual qualification for the novel methodology under evaluation.
- CHMP Qualification Opinion on the acceptability of a specific use of the proposed method (e.g. use of a novel methodology or an imaging method) in a research and development (R&D) context (non-clinical or clinical studies), based on the assessment of submitted data

It is recognised that by utilising Qualification Advice Pathway for certain outcomes from the ConcePTION project we would be able to build support & recognition for these. Having regulatory endorsed methodologies would enable there to be acceptance of the data / evidence generated that could inform information contained within product label and Summaries of Product Characteristics (SmPCs). In addition, having methodologies endorsed by key Regulatory Body such as the EMA may have the potential for wider acceptance from other regulatory bodies of project results (FDA, PMDA), global impact.

To help promote a common understanding of Qualification Advice pathway there have been consortium wide Webinar sessions held (August 2019 & January 2020). [Refer to Deliverable 6.1 appendix 4 for details]

EMA qualification advice: what is it & why?

- ‘The CHMP can issue an opinion on the acceptability of a specific use of a method, such as the use of a novel methodology or an imaging method in the context of research and development’
- Before final adoption of qualification opinion, the CHMP makes its evaluation open for public consultation by the scientific community. This ensures that the CHMP shares information, as agreed with the applicant, and is open to scientific scrutiny and discussion.
- The Agency publishes all CHMP qualification opinions.

Qualification Advice

- The CHMP can issue advice on protocols and methods that are intended to develop a novel method with the aim of moving towards qualification.
- The advice is based on the evaluation of the scientific rationale and on the preliminary data submitted to the Agency.
- Based on qualification advice, the Agency may propose a letter of support as an option, when the novel methodology under evaluation cannot yet be qualified but is shown to be promising based on preliminary data.
- Letters of support aim to encourage data-sharing and to facilitate studies aimed at eventual qualification for the novel methodology under evaluation.
- These letters include a high-level summary of the novel methodology, context of use, available data, and on-going and future investigations. The Agency publishes letters of support, if the sponsors agree.

Timeline for Qualification Advice

Innovation Task Force (ITF)

- The ITF is a multidisciplinary group that includes scientific, regulatory and legal competences. It was set up to ensure coordination across the Agency and to provide a forum for early dialogue with applicants on innovative aspects in medicines development. The ITF briefing meetings provide a forum for early dialogue on medicines innovation. They cover regulatory, technical and scientific issues arising from innovative medicines development, new technologies etc, and but ITF briefing meetings are intended to be much earlier than when one would normally seek scientific advice.

The objectives of the ITF are to:

- Establish a discussion platform for early dialogue with applicants, in particular micro, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), academics and researchers, to proactively identify scientific, legal and regulatory issues of emerging therapies and technologies;
- Address the impact of emerging therapies and technologies on current scientific, legal and regulatory requirements with the Agency's committees and their working parties;
- Identify the need for specialised expertise at an early stage;
- Provide advice on the eligibility to Agency procedures relating to research and development, in conjunction with the Committee for Medicinal Products for Human Use (CHMP), the Committee for Medicinal Products for Veterinary Use (CVMP), the European Commission and national competent authorities (NCAs) as appropriate, for example:
- Where there are uncertainties on whether the concerned therapy contains a medicinal substance;
- For borderline products (products for which there is uncertainty over whether they fit the definition of a medicinal product or not);

- For (medicinal) substances incorporated in medical devices for which the medicinal and ancillary functions are borderline;
- Review the regulatory and scientific implications of emerging therapies and technologies, in conjunction with the Agency's committees and their working parties;
- Increase awareness and learning in emerging therapies and technologies at the Agency.

ITF briefing meetings facilitate informal exchange of information and guidance in the development process, complementing and reinforcing existing formal procedures such as advanced-therapy-medicinal-product (ATMP) classification and certification, designation of orphan medicinal products and scientific advice.

The objectives are two-fold: firstly, for EMA to help clarify questions regarding the road to market of innovative medicines and secondly, to help ensure EMA awareness and preparedness for assessment of the most recent developments in innovative medicine.

The informal scientific brainstorming-discussions are led by experts from the Agency network, working parties and committees.

Information taken from EMA Website: [EMA Innovation Task Force](#)¹

WP 6 Evaluation: Our Strategy

As part of our overall strategy in working towards identifying suitable candidates within the project consortium for Qualification Advice it has been agreed that WPs will be required to attend an ITF briefing meeting. By doing this we intend to engage early with regulators and thus enabling early dialogue between the project WPs and EMA experts. The work carried out by the teams in preparation for ITF briefing meetings will contribute to ConcePTION preparations for regulatory processes.

¹ Information taken from EMA Website: [EMA Innovation Task Force](#)

Note, it is acknowledged that as a consortium member EMA will participate in early discussions with the different work packages. However, to avoid a conflict of interest EMA ConcePTION members will step away from discussions when a decision to follow the formal route of QA is initiated.

WP6 Evaluation: where we are as a consortium on topic of Qualification Advice

An 'SWOT' type evaluation of ConcePTION outcomes has been carried out. This activity highlights the 'value add' that seeking EMA endorsement on outcomes generated from ConcePTION and the significant impact on our strategies with regards to sustainability.

QA Decision Tree

Step 1: Work Packages to populate candidate template

(provided in Deliverable 6.1 Appendix 3)

- The template has been designed to help frame the work and enable deeper dive discussions between WP6 and individual WPs.

Step 2: EMA consortium member / WP6 informal review & feedback (WP6 facilitation)

- WP6 will review the information provided by WPs and will solicit feedback from EMA consortium members
- Work with WPs to prepare for Innovation Task Force meeting
 - For all EU Funded projects it has been agreed that the DoA is adequate for ITF Submission
 - Any supplementary information/ documentation team already has would be advantageous for ITF Members to see (avoiding duplication of effort for teams)
 - Team to consider what questions/ topics they would seek to have EMA input on

Step 3: MB Decision Making Step

MB Endorsement of proposed candidates for Innovation Task Force Meeting (EMA)

- MB asked to endorse proposed project candidates moving forward for innovation task force meeting
- WP6 will work in partnership with WPs to define strategy, timeframe, scheduling for ITF meeting.

Step 4: Innovation Task Force meeting

- WPs attend ITF Meeting
- Typically have 90 minute discussions with identified EMA scientific staff as well as scientific experts from the EU Regulatory Network
- Opportunity for consortium to explain what we are doing, specify scope of deliverables / project constraints to ITF dialogue to engage the regulators, and for EMA to provide input / clarity on next steps for QA

Step 5: MB Decision Making step

Outputs from ITF Meeting presented to MB for endorsements

- Following ITF meeting WPs will return to MB and update board members with discussions held
 - Were additional questions raised by ITF / would additional work be required to meet expectations

It is acknowledged by ConcePTION that Qualification Advice in particular, can be resource intensive to develop and will require a submission fee: within ConcePTION SME status will be utilised for this pathway. In parallel, work is ongoing to determine WP impact assessment of QA on WP workload / capacity and the preparation of a business case for seeking additional funding that will go to MB for endorsement prior to request for additional funding going forward.

Next steps

Work related to ConcePTION and the interaction with Regulatory Agencies will be on-going throughout the lifetime of the project. As the different work packages complete their activities, there will in parallel be, appropriate strategic planning put in place to ensure teams are prepared, peer review of scientific methodology and data generated occurs and that the appropriate internal review occurs prior to engagement with Regulatory bodies.

3. The ConcePTION Glossary

The ConcePTION project brings together many partners from different backgrounds including maternal health, medicines development, pharmacovigilance, clinical and life sciences research, mathematical modelling, health informatics, multiple stakeholder representatives and other disciplines. It aims to develop new forms of evidence that require very precisely formulated specification and documentation. For this reason, a project wide glossary was included in the description of action to be developed by WP6.

Work on the glossary was started by specifying its primary objectives.

1. To standardise the use of terms across the work packages and partners, in all of project deliverables and external stakeholder engagement materials.
2. To make sure that explanations of terms can be provided in a public friendly form, so that this can support the public version of the knowledge bank and public understanding of our other publishable outputs.

Through interaction with different public and industry work package 6 partners an inventory of topics for the glossary was compiled, along with an initial source that could be used to obtain suitable definitions.

Category	Initial sources of terms and definitions
Medicines (identification, constituents, administration)	open Medicine project
PK, PV	EMA/HMA, GVP, WP1, WP2, WP3 deliverables
Clinical trials (methodological terms)	GVP, EUPATI
Statistics	GVP, EUPATI
Regulatory	EUPATI
Healthcare (system, organisational structures, actors)	ISO standards, DigitalHealthEurope project
Information governance	GDPR, EMIF project, DigitalHealthEurope project
ICT	WP7 deliverables, DigitalHealthEurope project, EMIF project
Milk biobank	WP4 deliverables
Maternity	Online dictionaries
Biology	Online dictionaries
Explanatory definitions	EUPATI, Connected Health Cities

It was recognised that, in order to deliver a glossary that would eventually meet both of the objectives, it would be an advantage for each entry to be able to have (i) a scientific definition and (ii) an explanation that would be suitable for members of the public, especially women of childbearing age but also people from any of the many disciplines listed above who might be unfamiliar with terms from another discipline.

It is important for the glossary to adopt and promote the use of well accepted definitions, and so this glossary does not propose definitions but references authoritative sources that are trusted in the field and already well adopted by others. The glossary's purpose is to help to support unambiguous interpretation of project outputs.

After initial compilation, the draft glossary was shared with other work packages to confirm their acceptance of the structure, and to verify or supplement terms from their disciplines and work package areas.

A glossary cannot be correct indefinitely, since better definitions can sometimes be found or

become accepted later. Nor can its explanations be ideal: they will be improved with feedback from different user groups. Inevitably, some important terms will have been overlooked and will need to be added. For this reason, we regard the glossary as a living repository. It will be maintained by WP6 throughout the project.

The need for a project glossary is not unique to ConcePTION. In parallel to this work, at least two other European projects, in which partner i~HD is involved, have identified a similar need. There are many terms in common across these projects. Collaboration with them has been agreed, and enables us to share the maintenance workload and to maximise the consistent use of terms across Europe. We have therefore agreed across these initial projects to centralise the compilation of the glossary efforts through i~HD. Once implemented, we will promote wider adoption and collaboration, including with new IMI projects.

Shortly after the publication of this deliverable, it will be migrated to an online tool being developed by i~HD where it can be more easily consulted, critiqued, and improved. Although it is still a prototype and still being implemented, example screenshots are included below to indicate the intended look and feel of the online glossary.

List concepts

[Add new concept](#)
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Click on a term to view the concept.

Showing 1 to 25 of 643 entries

Search:

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[Previous](#)
[1](#)
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[...](#)
[26](#)
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Term	ID	Main term	Synonymid	Definition	Validated	Project		
"post-it" function	90	No	0	Yes	No	EuroRec		
abuse of medicinal products	535	No	0	Yes	No	openMedicine		
academic institution	580	No	0	Yes	No	openMedicine		
access level	127	No	0	No	No	EuroRec		
access management policy	116	No	0	No	No	EuroRec		
accessory	638	No	0	Yes	No	openMedicine		
ACS	477	No	0	Yes	No	openMedicine		
active ingredient	163	No	0	Yes	No	openMedicine		
active marker	425	No	0	Yes	No	openMedicine		
active pharmaceutical ingredient	634	No	0	Yes	No	openMedicine		
active substance	524	No	0	Yes	No	openMedicine		
actor	110	No	0	No	No	EuroRec		

Viewing the glossary list of terms without any filter. Some of the columns on display have still to be refined.

List concepts

[Add new concept](#)
[How to read this table?](#)
All

Click on a term to view the concept.

Showing 1 to 8 of 8 entries (filtered from 643 total entries)

Search:

Show entries

Previous **1** Next

Term	ID	Main term	Synonymid	Definition	Validated	Project		
administrable dose form	203	No	0	Yes	No	openMedicine		
administration	82	No	0	Yes	No	EuroRec		
administration device	152	No	0	Yes	No	openMedicine		
administration method	334	No	0	Yes	No	openMedicine		
administrative authorisation	33	No	0	No	No	EuroRec		
administrative data	120	No	0	No	No	EuroRec		
route of administration	277	No	0	Yes	No	openMedicine		
Test term Admin	687	No	0	Yes	No	EuroRec		

Showing 1 to 8 of 8 entries (filtered from 643 total entries)

Search:

Show entries

Previous **1** Next

Filtering the list using the letters “admin”. When finished, it will also be possible to filter the list by project (e.g. ConcePTION) or by category (e.g. pharmacovigilance).

View concept: administrable dose form

[Back to list of concepts](#)
[Edit concept administrable dose form](#)

Project: openMedicine Comments: Synonym(s): Has no synonym(s).	Abbreviation: No Status finalised: No
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Definitions for the selected concept

- pharmaceutical dose form for administration to the patient, after any necessary transformation of the manufactured dose form has been carried out.

Reference: ISO 11615:2012
Created: 09/05/2015
- pharmaceutical dose form as administered to the patient, after any necessary transformation of the packaged pharmaceutical dose form has been carried out

Reference: [ISO 1616:2012]
Created: 19/05/2015

Viewing the definitions available for a term, as seen by a conventional user who does not have editing rights. In this screen the term has two definitions (although here, they are the same text). Each one can have a reference for the definition and a URL to the source. Each term can have synonyms and abbreviations.

Edit concept: administrable dose form

[Back to list of concepts](#) [View concept](#)

In case plural has been used, please correct into singular.

Term*:

Project*: openMedicine EuroRec

Category*: ICT Health care

Abbreviation:

Status finalised:

Comments:

B I U

[Save term & project & comments \(concept\)](#)

Definitions:

<p>Definition 1:</p> <p>pharmaceutical dose form for administration to the patient, after any necessary transformation of the manufactured dose form has been carried out.</p> <p>Meta data: Reference: ISO 11615:2012 Created: 09/05/2015 Updated: 19/05/2015</p> <p>Edit Delete</p>	<p>Definition 2:</p> <p>pharmaceutical dose form as administered to the patient, after any necessary transformation of the packaged pharmaceutical dose form has been carried out</p> <p>Meta data: Reference: [ISO 1616:2012] Created: 19/05/2015 Updated: 17/11/2015</p> <p>Edit Delete</p>
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Each project participating in the glossary (such as ConcePTION) will be asked to nominate a few “Glossary managers” who will have the rights to add, edit or delete term entries, add terms to their project from the database, categorise terms, make comments (for example, working notes when drafting a new entry). Entries can be draft or finalised.

Definitions:

<p>Definition 1:</p> <p>pharmaceutical dose form for administration to the patient, after any necessary transformation of the manufactured dose form has been carried out.</p> <p>Meta data: Reference: ISO 11615:2012 Created: 09/05/2015 Updated: 19/05/2015</p> <p>Edit Delete</p>	<p>Definition 2:</p> <p>pharmaceutical dose form as administered to the patient, after any necessary transformation of the packaged pharmaceutical dose form has been carried out</p> <p>Meta data: Reference: [ISO 1616:2012] Created: 19/05/2015 Updated: 17/11/2015</p> <p>Edit Delete</p>
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Modify selected definition: ⓘ

Definition:

pharmaceutical dose form for administration to the patient, after any necessary transformation of the manufactured dose form has been carried out.

Reference:

Reference URL:

Comment:

This screen shows the editing of a definition. All of the long text fields (definitions, comments) can support rich text formatting.

The public (open access) version of the ConcePTION glossary is now online, and may be accessed from <https://glossary.ramit.be/public/home.cfm?pid=5>. A cross-workpackage editorial group has been appointed, who will share the maintenance of this glossary.

Appendix 1: European Medicines Agency - Regulatory Science and H2020

Webinar presentation (24 Sep 2020)

EUROPEAN MEDICINES AGENCY
SCIENCE MEDICINES HEALTH

Regulatory Support to EU Research

OPEN INFO DAY Horizon 2020 'Health, demographic change and wellbeing'
Wednesday, 3 July 2019
Brussels

Presented by Corinne de Vries
Head of Science & Innovation Support, Human Medicines Research & Development Support Division

EUROPEAN MEDICINES AGENCY

Declaration of Interests

I am full staff member of the European Medicines Agency and I do not have interests that might pose a conflict with my duties.

1 OPEN INFO DAY Horizon 2020 'Health, demographic change and wellbeing' 8 October 2020

EUROPEAN MEDICINES AGENCY

Outline

- Regulating medicines in EU
- Framework of collaboration with Academia: why - what - how
- 'Health, demographic change and well-being' Work Programme 2018-2020
- Conclusions
- Q&A

2 OPEN INFO DAY Horizon 2020 'Health, demographic change and wellbeing' 8 October 2020

EUROPEAN MEDICINES AGENCY

The European medicines regulatory network

Closely-coordinated regulatory network of national competent authorities (~50), European Medicines Agency (EMA) and the European Commission
Collaborative operational model within the EU and internationally

3 OPEN INFO DAY Horizon 2020 'Health, demographic change and wellbeing' 8 October 2020

EUROPEAN MEDICINES AGENCY

How are medicines approved?

Centralised procedure (via EMA) National procedures (via NCAs)

4 OPEN INFO DAY Horizon 2020 'Health, demographic change and wellbeing' 8 October 2020

EUROPEAN MEDICINES AGENCY

Medicines approved through the EMA centralised procedure

Centralised Procedure Mandatory for new medicines to treat:

- [human immunodeficiency virus \(HIV\)](#) or acquired immune deficiency syndrome (AIDS)
- [cancer](#)
- [diabetes](#)
- [neurodegenerative diseases](#)
- [auto-immune and other immune dysfunctions](#)
- [viral diseases](#)
- [medicines derived from biotechnology processes, such as genetic engineering](#)
- [advanced therapy medicines](#), such as gene-therapy, somatic cell-therapy or tissue-engineered medicines
- [orphan medicines](#) (medicines for rare diseases)
- [veterinary medicines for use as growth or yield enhancers](#).

It is **optional** for other medicines:

- containing new active substances for indications other than those stated above
- that are a **significant therapeutic, scientific or technical innovation**

These substances would be in the **interest of public or animal health at EU level**

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Regulators became gatekeepers and enablers...

Gatekeepers:

- Changing landscape of pharmaceutical R&D
- Timeline to R&D
- Summary processes
- Increasing development costs
- Increasing regulatory demands
- Changing markets
- Multistakeholder involvement

Enablers:

- Creation of adaptive regulatory frameworks
- Creation of multistakeholder interaction
- Addressing unmet regulatory needs
- Explore and resolve innovative financing
- Quantification of benefit/risk
- Enable innovative clinical trial designs and data systems
- Create personalized medicine

Proactive regulatory approach: regulators as "enablers"

Clinical pharmacology & Therapeutics: Advance online publication: 3 April 2013. doi:10.1038/clpt.2013.14 | F. Ehrman, M. Papalica Armeti, T. Salmanson, W. Paoletti, S. Varnabas, R. Hammings, T. G. Esler and C. Schneider

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What support do we provide at EMA?

Development support initiatives
optimising use of existing legal tools

- Legal tools**
 - Conditional MA
 - Accelerated assessment
 - CHMP opinion on compassionate use
 - Orphan designation
 - ATMP classification
 - SME office
 - Scientific advice
- Content concept**
Adaptive pathways defines the product development route
 - Expansion/confirmation
 - Involvement of stakeholders
 - Use of Real World Data

PRIME

- Innovation Task Force
- EU-innovation network
- Framework for interaction with Academia

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EMA framework of collaboration with academia

"EMA wants to move to a new level of collaboration with academia."

Academia play an important role in the EU medicines regulatory network.

Interaction with EU regulators can help academia translate their discoveries into patient-focused medicines.

Working more closely together will bring great benefits to public health".

Guido Rasi, EMA Executive Director

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Academia and EMA web pages; facilitate communication

Academia

EMA supports

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Marketing authorisations by SMEs

Most frequent major objections in SME applications – human medicines

Objection Category	Percentage
Quality	46%
Clinical Efficacy	36%
Clinical Safety	11%
Non-Clinical	7%

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SME Office: tailoring assistance to SMEs

A strategic regulatory toolbox to promote innovation & development of new medicines by SMEs:

- A single interface, facilitate communication
- SME assignment, public SME register
- Fee incentives, regulatory assistance, translations
- News bulletins, SME user guide, workshops
- Certification procedures for SMEs in relation to ATMP developments

sme@ema.europa.eu
http://www.ema.europa.eu/doc/en_GB/document_library/Regulatory_and_procedural_guideline/2009/10/WC508004134.pdf

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Did you know?

EMA Innovation Task Force (ITF)

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Innovation Task Force - Objectives:

- **early dialogue** on **scientific, legal and regulatory** issues
- **knowledge exchange** on innovative strategies involving **EU network**
- **address the impact of emerging therapies and technologies** on current regulatory system
- identify the **need for specialised expertise** at an early stage
- understand concerns and **enable solution** finding
- identify issue of particular interest to regulators in **preparing for formal procedures** (e.g. biomarkers qualifications, scientific advice)

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Emerging Technologies:

Novel treatment technologies:

- Genome editing
- 3D printing of viable cells
- Externally activated products (magnetic / photo)
- Microbiomics
- M-health and E-health (Apps)
- Disease modelling
- Treatment algorithms (CT → software)
- Epigenetics

Novel manufacturing technologies:

- Nanotechnology
- Biomaterials
- Continuous manufacturing / QbD

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Users of the Innovation Task Force

Originator and the marketing authorization holder for 94 approved products evaluated, divided according to organization type

Regulatory watch: When do new medicines originate from in the EU? Nature Reviews Drug Discovery Volume: 13, Pages: 92-93, Published online 31 January 2014

Consortium

Since 2016 the ITF supports informal meetings with research and public-private funded consortia, e.g. IMI, HZ 2020, FP7 etc.

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Qualification of Novel Methodologies

- Regulatory validity and acceptability of a method in medicines life-cycle R&D context
- Scientific pathway for innovative methods and tools (e.g. biomarkers, in silico models, e-health)
- Joint qualification EMA/FDA can be requested
- Clear outcomes:
 - Letter of support, OR
 - Qualification Advice, OR
 - Qualification Opinion

Essential considerations when preparing for scientific advice on new methodologies now published on the EMA H2020 web page.

<http://www.ema.europa.eu/en/h2020/Qualification-of-novel-methodologies-for-drug-development-guidance-to-applicants>

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Did you know? Novel Methodologies

- Animal Models
- Biomarkers
- In silico-models
- Clinical Outcome Assessment (COA) (End-points, PRO, ClinRO, ObsRO)
- Imaging Markers
- Symptom Scales
- Statistical Methods

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EMA Scientific Advice and Protocol assistance

Outcome of the November 2017 CHMP meeting in relation to scientific advice procedures

Final scientific advice procedures

Substance	Intended indication(s)	Type of request				Pharma clinical	Pre-clinical	Clinical	Scientific Benefit
		SA	PA	SA	PA				
Biological	Treatment of Clostridium difficile infection.	x				x	x	x	
Chemical	Reduction of risk of cardiovascular death in chronic kidney disease.	x						x	
Biological	Treatment of Farber disease.			x			x	x	
Biological	Treatment of Farber disease.				x			x	
Chemical	Weight management.	x					x	x	
Chemical	Treatment of enteral feeding intolerance.	x					x	x	

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PRIME scheme - Goal & Scope

To foster the development of **medicines with major public health interest**.

- Reinforce scientific and regulatory advice
 - Foster and facilitate early interaction
 - Raise awareness of requirements earlier in development
- Optimise development for robust data generation
 - Focus efficient development
 - Promote generation of robust and high quality data
- Enable accelerated assessment
 - Promote generation of high quality data
 - Facilitated by knowledge gained throughout development

Building on existing framework; Eligibility according to existing Accelerated Assessment criteria

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Support to medicines innovation at National level

National Competent Authorities (NCAs) responsible for key tasks, including

- [Authorisation and Good Manufacturing and Lab Practices](#)
- [Clinical trial authorisation](#)
- [ATMPs Hospital Exemption](#)
- [Compassionate use](#)
- [NCAs scientific advice \(fees might apply\)](#)
- [NCAs Innovation Offices: specific schemes/services \(fees might apply\) including decision on applicable framework \(e.g. device or medicine\)](#)

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Concerted Support Action (CSA)
Strengthen *Regulatory Sciences* and support for regulatory *Scientific Advice*

EU Innovation Network
Outreach opportunity 2018–2020

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Regulatory science projects

Considerations: as strategic and effective as possible

- Resource implications
- Conflict of interest – perceived or real
- Alignment with Network Strategy 2020
- Impact on EU public health
- Existing opportunities for regulatory interaction
- Not at the bidding stage – no competitive (dis)advantage

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EMA INVOLVEMENT IN EXTERNALLY FUNDED PROJECTS

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In summary

- Please help ensure the environment is ready for the products of your scientific excellence
- Regulatory awareness and considerations can tangibly enhance the translation and impact of your research programme in development tools and treatments for patients
- Platforms for dialogue, guidelines and scientific advice readily available for innovators both at national and EU level: speak at an early stage with us, plan ahead, consider investment of time and fees
- Make best use of the EMA Framework and webpages for collaboration with Academia and of Regulators' outreach activities
- Register with EMA SME office for support

Welcome in the European Regulatory Science eco-system

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Thank you for your attention

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Clinical Trial Information System (CTIS)

- EMA, Member States and Sponsors working closely together to prepare the system for audit.
- EMA has revised the CTIS project methodology and plan to improve delivery.
- Sponsor representatives from both industry and academia are involved in close contact with the developer.
- In June 2019, CTIS enters a phase of agile, iterative delivery, to prepare the system for audit.
- It will then be further enhanced for go-live and beyond, in close cooperation with the user community.

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